

Valency Patterns of TAKE in EFL and ESL

Yating Tao (University of Louvain, Belgium)

English as a foreign language (EFL), also known as Learner Englishes (e.g. English used in China), and English as a second language (ESL), also known as New Englishes (e.g. English used in Singapore), have long been studied in two individual fields, namely Contact Linguistics and Second Language Acquisition, thus leading to a “paradigm gap” (Sridhar & Sridhar, 1986). Despite their differences (e.g. language input and functions), EFL and ESL varieties seem to share the same psycholinguistic processes of second language acquisition (Buschfeld, 2013; Percillier, 2016). Some studies also report a fuzzy borderline between ESL and EFL varieties (e.g. Cyprus in Buschfeld, 2013; Tswana English in Gilquin & Granger, 2011). Further, ESL varieties are not necessarily the result of colonization (Buschfeld and Kautzsch, 2014 on Namibia; Edwards on the Netherlands, 2014).

Against this backdrop, this study aims to bridge the gap between these two types of English varieties at the lexis-grammar interface, which is argued to be particularly prone to innovation (Schneider, 2007). More specifically, I focus on the valency patterns of TAKE in two corpora: student writing samples from the Hong Kong and Singapore components of the International Corpus of English (ICE) and Chinese student essays from the International Corpus of Learner English (ICLE), with British university student essays from the Louvain Corpus of Native English Essays (LOCNESS) as a reference. The valency patterns of TAKE are analyzed at two levels. At the higher level, all instances of TAKE are classified in the manner of valency pattern, that is, by distinguishing between valency patterns with it, monovalency, divalency, trivalency and quadrivalency and their subcategories. At the lower level, I examine phraseological uses including phrasal verbs, light verb constructions and idioms. To detect the potential links in valency patterns and phraseological uses among these English varieties, I employ chi-square test and hierarchical clustering analysis.

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